

India's Foreign Policy Shift towards Palestine and Israel

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Abstract:

In 1992, signs of change began in India's foreign policy towards Palestine and Israel. New attitudes had been noticed in the United Nations as India backed Israel. Two years later, the Palestinian issue no longer attracts the Indian government's interest, especially since the Oslo Accords of 1994. This research study attempts to explain the reasons for India's shift in foreign policy toward Palestine and Israel. The reasons that prompted the Indian leadership to adopt a new approach in India's foreign policy towards the two sides of the Palestinian-Israeli conflict in a way different from the previous policy indicates the existence of significant continuity and change to achieve the specific objectives of the Indian foreign policy. The research seeks to delve into the facts on the ground to understand the factors of transformation in foreign policy by clarifying the interaction between ideas and the political, economic and security flows related to building an effective international relationship. The used methodology to respond to the study's questions is focused on taking an objective, analytical, and descriptive approach. The research was qualitative in nature and scope, focusing on narratives and evaluations of chronological historical events and including original analysis before drawing findings. The research showed that there is a shift in India's foreign policy towards Israel due to several factors highly considered by the Indian and the Israeli governments. Supporting and keeping a hard position with the Palestinians and their issue against Israel is no longer useful. India gave the priority to developing its relations with Israel in order to achieve its national interests by going in a new direction instead of sticking with obstacles in the way of political, economic, and security flourishing.

Keywords: Foreign Policy; India; Relations; Israel: Palestinian; Change; cooperation.

Historical background of India's foreign policy towards Palestine and Israel:

While a number of scholars believe that the Indian government is still dealing with the Palestinian issue. The objective of India's foreign policy by maintaining good relations with the official Palestinian side is to use it as a pressure card against Israel. There is a shift in the Indian Foreign Policy towards Palestine and Israel because the Indian foreign policy did support Israel in the United Nations. India carried out this transformation process based on several reasons, the most important of which is the prospects for Indian-Israeli cooperation in security and the economy, and based on India's desire to reach the ranks of advanced countries economically and militarily to gain greater influence internationally, enabling it to play a greater role on the international scene like the rest of the great countries China, the United States, and Russia.

India's economic growth has led it to aspire to be one of the influential in the world by adopting a political realist approach in the field of foreign relations. This article aims to identify India's position on the Palestinian-Israeli issue as one of the areas of Indian foreign policy. India linked its fate to the Palestinians before its independence and continued in this state for a long period after its independence in 1947. The presence of the Palestinian Issue was clear and undeniable in the fabric of relations between India and Israel. Even after the establishment of relations with Israel in 1992, the classic Indian position on the Palestinian issue did not change. However, academics and scholars provided explanations for a new trend in a new relationship between Indo-Israeli and Indo-Palestinian relations. These changes have been led by India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi, Israel's new and welcome friend. Therefore, this article seeks to trace the changes in the position of the Indian authorities on the Palestinian issue since Modi came to power in May 2014 until the present, and to discuss the reasons for the changes taking place in the field of Indian foreign relations towards Palestine and Israel.

In the presence of a number of factors such as religion, anti-imperialism, anti-colonialism and non-identifying politics has shaped India's attitude towards the Palestinian issue over years. Initially, the Muslim community in India was the target and center of the struggle between the Indian National Congress and the Muslim League movement. (Azad, 2021).

The Indian Muslims would be harnessed to struggle with the Palestinians for national liberation. The transfer of the Israel issue to the United Nations caused India to become an important behind-the-scenes player for the Jewish Agency in the deliberation process - as it negatively and positively affects the establishment of the State of Israel. However, with the establishment of Israel and the outbreak of wars with the Arabs, India has always expressed its strong support for the Arabs and the Palestinians.

In contrast to the faltering support of the Arab states to the belligerents, Israel gave its full support to India in its war against Pakistan in 1965 and its war against Bangladesh in 1971, by providing support to India through artillery equipment (Datta, 2013). Therefore, the perception was reinforced that the Indian alliance with Israel was normal, and that Israel's victory in the Six-Day War of 1967 was acceptable in relation to India's victory over Pakistan in 1965.

India continued the same formula in foreign policy. It attempted to attend various Islamic conferences, publicly condemned Israel's actions and at the same time, sent medical supplies to the victims of Israeli wars. India supported the participation of the Palestine Liberation Organization as a UN observer. In 1974, India voted with United Nations Resolution 3379, which defines Zionism as racism. But in 1975-1977 the Janata Party opposed Prime Minister Indira Gandhi's "emergency policy", causing many supporters of Israel to return to the Indian Parliament and raise expectations in Jerusalem for a change in the status quo (Kumaraswamy, 2010, p. 181).

In the late 1980s, a change occurred in the Indian government's policy towards Israel. The reasons for the change were multidimensional. Domestically, the hostility of Israel began to reduce as a new party dominated in 1989 formatting a base for change. At the regional level, fundamentalist terrorism has brought India and Israel closer together (. At the same time, lower crude oil prices have reduced the ability of Arab countries to exert pressure through oil, as they have done in the past. This was accompanied by the fact that India was discovering the strength of the United States, and it needed it to get out of the economic crisis. The Soviet Union's collapse by 1991 announced a new era of the world order causing an unbalance between the international major powers leading to the unipolar system headed dominated by the United States. India's hostility to Israel has been an obstacle in its relations with the United States, but a general change

in policy is made easier in light of negotiations between Israel and the Palestinians after the Madrid Conference.

Even with creating new ties with the Israelis in 1992, the Indian government kept its usual support given to the Palestinians. These good relations have been maintained through mutual visits, financial donations, cooperation, and constant condemnation of Israel. The Palestinian cause has remained popular in India, and recently formed a fertile ground for BDS activities in the subcontinent.

Changes in Indian foreign policy with regard to the Palestinian issue:

Indian aid during the period following India's independence, until the establishment of the Palestinian Authority in 1994, consisted of holding military training courses for members of Fatah movement and other Palestinian leftist organizations, and as a result of Indian solidarity with Arab issues, foremost of which is the Palestinian issue, especially through the Non-Aligned Movement The Palestinians were able to find a foothold in India and benefit from its military experience. In addition, many Palestinian students at this stage benefited from the educational grants offered by Indian universities. For example, the number of Palestinian students who were studying in universities Between 1990 and 1991, there were about 9,111 Indian students, and this number is large when compared to the number of Palestinian students studying in universities in some developing countries.

Prime Minister Modi's rise to power in 2014 marked a change in the history of Indian foreign policy, as well as changes in relations between India and the Palestinian Authority. The ruling right-wing party announced important reforms in India's foreign relations, putting three major issues on the agenda: leading a tough line on India's national security, accelerating the second phase of neoliberal reforms, and culminating the idea of cultural nationalism. The changing attitude towards the Middle East is one of the developing areas in the issue of Indian external relations(Kasturi, 2015).

In order to examine the changes in Indian foreign policy with regard to the Palestinian issue, this cannot be separated from the changes in relations between Israel and India as they are parallel schemes that are difficult to separate (GERBERG, 2008, pp. 181-182). The strengthening of relations can be examined from several activities and practices: security,

diplomatic visits, changing public relations and voting patterns in the United Nations.

In the field of security, in recent years, Israel has strengthened its security relations with India, making India one of its main export destinations. The fact that Israel is the fourth-largest supplier of arms to India came to light. The number of diplomatic visits between the two countries has increased steadily since the establishment and development of diplomatic relations.

During the annual meeting of the United Nations General Assembly in September 2014, Indian Prime Minister Modi met with Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu to discuss Iran's nuclear program and to expand cooperation (NINGTHOUJAM, 2014). In October of the same year, the President of India made a historic visit to Israel. Mutual visits between the two parties have followed.

The United Nations has become one of the most interesting arenas for studying changes in India's external relations. India's voting pattern shows loyalty to support the Palestinians and clear anti-Israel. Apparently, in order to balance its support for Israel, India voted to set up a special commission of inquiry in Gaza on behalf of the UN Human Rights Council (Human Rights Council, 2018). Finally, India announced that it was "expressing concern" fearing an escalation of violence between Israel and the Palestinians. In July 2015, India, along with countries such as Ethiopia, Kenya, Paraguay and Macedonia, abstained from voting in favor of a UN report condemning Israel in light of the military operation against the Gaza Strip. The Palestinian ambassador to India, Adnan Abu Al-Haija, described India's decision as "shocking" and said India's decision was affected by the military relationship between Israel and India.

Indian sources reported that Netanyahu personally contacted Modi and asked him to abstain from the vote. On August 8, 2015, Indian External Affairs Minister Swaraj Sharma, in an effort to reach the hearts of the Arab and Muslim public, emphasized that there had been no change in India's policy towards the Palestinian Authority, and that India's support for the Palestinian struggle remained strong.

The Minister emphasized that India continues to pursue a unique policy of non-interference, non-judgment and non-compliance. In other

words, India is ready to continue providing support to the Palestinians, but it is preferable that they themselves decide their own fate.

Some argue that the change in policy toward Israel began before the advent of the Modi government, specifically, during the “Kargil Crisis” in May 1999. This happened when the supply of arms from Israel allowed India to win the war against Pakistan. Since 2012, India has expressed "concern" but has not condemned Israel's actions against Palestinian citizens. Although India remained supportive of a sovereign Palestinian state based on the 1967 lines, its expressions of support for the Palestinian Authority gradually changed. Since Modi took over as Prime Minister, India-Israel relations have practically been reset. The Indian vote is a symbol of the ongoing rapprochement between the governments of Israel and India. India's abstention does not symbolize neutrality, on the contrary. It is a diplomatic escape from embarrassment with both Palestinians and Israelis. After many years of active pro-Palestinian policy at the United Nations, this marked a change in Indian foreign policy.

Reasons behind the shifts if India's foreign policy:

Foreign policy rarely serves one goal. It is usually used to achieve goals such as security, assistance, trade, or prestige. Most countries in the world tend to adhere enthusiastically to the fundamental principles that guide their foreign policy. No doubt Indian foreign policy was shaped by its first prime minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, whose touches continued even after his death. His activity was in the field of international relations, including the economy of India in the global market. A major change in Indian foreign policy followed since the days of the struggle for its independence. The struggle in India continues over the correct way to conduct its foreign policy to meet the new challenges it faces.

There are several factors led to the current Indian foreign policy.

1. Establishing India's Position as a Major Power:

With the end of the colonial period and India gaining independence, the main task of the state of India was to strengthen and establish the new state. Admittedly, India as a country did not have a planned foreign policy. Its Prime Minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, created the vision of the cosmopolitan country. After that, the experience of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs developed, its diplomatic experience, which enabled it to conduct better management.

With the rise to power of Lal Bahadur Shastri, India's second prime minister, the Indian bureaucracy became dominant and replaced India's global concerns with domestic and regional concerns. The focus was on arranging the internal situation in the country, such as economic nationalism and anti-colonialism. In these years, foreign relations were mobilized to deal with the country's internal problems (Kumaraswamy, 2010, pp. 218-219).

The main change in Indian foreign policy lies in the transition from the messianic political diplomat, who sanctified idealism, to being guided by realism. The realist school argues that states constantly seek power which is expressed primarily in military capabilities (Öniş & Gençer, 2018, p. 15). India saw itself as promoting values such as pacifism, non-identification, cooperation, and democratic self-determination, and of course it was not ideal but rather beneficial. This became India's path to reach a unique and independent position among the countries of the world.

One of the reasons that led to the realization that the approach to political realism should be done gradually is the tensions with China and Pakistan. While arming themselves and calling for the help of a mighty power, India sank into internal problems. On this approach, relations with Israel were in line with these indications of a realistic vision from the Indian administration. It was represented in the Israeli military aid to India in the 1965 war with Pakistan and in 1971 in Bangladesh.

Prior to India's foreign exchange crisis in the early 1990s, Indian foreign policy was characterized by the search for external support. This mission was not inconsistent with its evolving needs. India's economic development strategy in its early years emphasized the importance of government regulation.

Trade with India has been characterized by high tariffs and structural barriers making it the most restrictive in Asia. During the 1980s, India launched reforms to facilitate imports, but its trade policy remained limited. India turned to the International Monetary Fund (IMF) for help. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) set conditions to support it. One of these conditions is the reform of trade policy (Dash, 1999, pp. 15-16). So India came under pressure to compete in the global market, the absence of Soviet support caused Indian diplomacy to be classified as an "unknown country".

Market conditions dictated the needs of India, which focused on the search for foreign investors and access to new markets. The economic

reforms were slow but fruitful, and enabled India to achieve rapid growth (Ahluwalia, 2002, p. 85). The Indian state has created a basis for changing its relations with major and regional powers as well as with its competitors - China and Pakistan. Over eight years, India's annual growth rate has increased by 13 percent, thanks to the system of open trade and foreign investment. The rate of growth and economic prosperity of India has accelerated to the third place in the world in terms of GDP. Economic growth coincided with several factors such as military and nuclear power, significantly increased economic prosperity, and future population growth with a young population.

India is seeking to strengthen its position in the group of countries with potential for economic development (BRICS), which also includes Russia, Brazil, China and South Africa, in order to strengthen itself in the global arena (Boehler & Teddy, 2014). It is BRICS that complicates India's position on Israel. Given the great respect that India enjoys in such organizations as well as from countries like Iran and the Arab Gulf states, the rapprochement between India, Israel and the United States is forcing India to walk a tightrope.

2. Finding a Place among Nations:

India believed in its ability to play an important role in the world arena and values its status as a power. But it did not receive the respect it deserves from the countries of the world. The stereotype that India once acquired is that it is a developing country in need of outside help. In addition, the long-term support for the Arab countries in general and the Palestinian cause in particular, did not lead to India being considered a source of strength in the policies of the countries of the world.

With the economic and military intensification of India, the need arose to re-examine the image of the nation. In the past decade, this field appears to have undergone drastic changes. The results are remarkable, with India now at the top of the list of third world countries with a long history of expertise in computing, media and services. All these considerations are in line with India's desire to strengthen its relations with Israel, which has experience in similar fields.

3. Transitions in regional power relations:

A number of events in the Middle East and other regions such as the "Arab Spring", the Syrian Civil War and Chinese militarization of the Indian

Ocean triggered a process of reassessment of alliances. The present government of India views the Middle East as its expanded neighborhood, as it is vital to India's national interests (Michael, 2013, p 60). India has witnessed the world's acceptance of the success of Islamists in Tunisia and Egypt, as well as global rejection of the emergence of the Islamic State (ISIS). At the same time, there is growing concern that instability in the Middle East is causing an increase in terrorism in India.

India is a major energy consumer, importing 68 percent of its oil from the Persian Gulf. Thus, any interruption in the country's regular energy supply could hinder its economic progress. As well as the amount of revenue transferred to foreign labor by about seven million workers in the Gulf countries (KT. 2016.).

Fears of change led to an increase in India's military purchases. The volume of defense trade between Israel and India since Modi took office during 2015 has reached \$695 million. This amount is greater than the volume of trade exchange between the two countries in the three years prior to its rise. These changes are in line with India's attitude toward Israel, which are a military power and a source of advanced technology.

In recent years, the United States has gradually tightened its relations with India, which has become a rising power in the East. Once the two parties dispel the doubts that characterized their relationship, they are able to defend their global and regional interests. Respectively, New Delhi's position on progress in the Iranian nuclear program has become a benchmark for Washington with respect to India. India's policy towards the Iranian nuclear file has been characterized by extreme caution from several angles, the most important of which are energy, military strength and commercial strategies.

The period of tensions between India and the United States after the sanctions ended with the signing of a nuclear agreement between the two powers in July 2015. The strengthening of relations between the two countries provided a new policy on India's participation in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict.

An Indian policy emerged that India's rising power, its deep commitment over the years to the Palestinian issue and its good relations with Israel could enable it to create a multi-faceted agreement in which each side in the conflict would enjoy the support of both sides (Tripathy, 2013, p.

166). India's emergence as another mediator in the long-running conflict would allow it to sweep the United States once again. This role is in line with the renaming of India as a great power. Why not, India is already seeking a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council and to highlight its uniqueness as a bridge of tolerance. This is accompanied by a change in the Palestinians, as the Palestinians continued to view the United States as an important but not objective mediator.

4. The New Indian Policy:

Before Narendra Modi's rise to power, he emerged as a representative of a new generation in Indian politics that advocated entrenched economic pragmatism. This was demonstrated when Modi was heading the Nationalist Party. This view was expressed even during his days as a state minister in the northwestern Indian state of Gujarat. He had a relationship with Israeli politicians, as he visited Israel during his tenure in this position (NDTV, 2015).

From the beginning of his tenure as Prime Minister, Modi has cultivated the assertion of India's pragmatic Indian foreign policy as necessary to achieve India's economic goals. The key to this transformation is that the Indian economy cannot survive without rapid industrialization. And that the government should pursue a neo-liberal policy. (Maitreesh & Roy, 2014).

During India's election period, Modi received a lot of money from businessmen, looking to speed up capital operations. After his election, he created a suitable working environment, reduced bureaucratic procedures and improved infrastructure. It seems that the idea was originally inspired by the Chinese model. The government wants to make India an industrial center that can compete rather than compete globally. One notable example of this policy is the "Made in India" programme, which aims to attract foreign investment while boosting domestic industry (Poudel, 2015).

Modi formulated India's relations with the relevant countries in order to achieve consistency with the policies of economic growth. This is fully in line with the markets in which Israel specializes for its export products, such as high technology, agriculture, communications and security. So far, much of India's foreign policy has been driven by its competition with countries such as Pakistan and China. But India under Modi is more focused on taking

advantage of opportunities to redefine its role in the region. (Ying, 2018, p. 2).

In this regard, Modi continues the steps of the "ruling Congress", which at that time established relations with Israel when the timing was right. Both Modi and his party see relations with Israel as an organic alliance of its domestic and regional interests. In addition, the personal relations between the leaders of the two countries Modi and Netanyahu before losing the election should not be ignored. Similarities can be found in the worldviews of both leaderships in several things, such as support for the conservative, right-wing and capitalist line (Kumaraswamy, 2017).

Discussion:

Since India's independence from Britain, India has devoted its efforts to decolonization and defending the issues of the occupied peoples, including the Palestinian issue. The Palestinians considered India one of the most important ally and supportive countries in international forums. India was one of the non-Arab countries that voted against the United Nations plan to partition Palestine, a plan that led to the establishment of the State of Israel. India recognized the Palestine Liberation Organization and decided to open a representative office for it in 1975. In addition, India It has made some diplomatic moves in the interest of the Palestinians to complement what was started by the first Prime Minister of India, Jawaharlal Nehru, and then Indira Gandhi, who ruled for 4 terms (Kumaraswamy, 2010, p. 25). India has adhered to policies similar to those of Arab countries towards the Palestinian issue. India refused normalization with Israel. This was accompanied by the rise of the voice of the Indian left movement, which believes in the dependence and linkage of the Zionist project to the imperialist West. Added to this is the Indian government's desire to boost its popularity among the Muslim minority, which represents one fifth of the population, by manipulating sympathy for Palestine.

The Shift In Indian Foreign Policy:

Something new happened in 1977 when the Morarji Desai government came to power in India coinciding with a major breakthrough in Arab-Israeli relations after Egyptian President Anwar Sadat visited the Israeli Knesset and delivered a speech there in the same year. This great Arab transformation along with other factors prompted India to open a gateway to talk with the Israelis, which ended with the establishment of diplomatic relations in 1992. Then the Bharatiya Janata Party came to power

in India in 1999, which strengthened and deepened relations between India and Israel. The party with a Hindu nationalist background believes that Hindus are the true sons of India and considers other Muslims or Christians as a threat to the security and identity of the country. (Madan, 2016)

The biggest factor in the development of the Indo-Israeli relationship is "arms and trade" (Beitelmair-Berini, 2018, pp. 167-169). The Indian-Israeli rapprochement became clear in 2015 when India abstained for the first time in its history on a draft resolution at the United Nations condemning the Israeli aggression on the Gaza Strip in 2014. This was a clear indication of the shape of the new relationship between the two countries, specifically between Modi and Netanyahu. The mutual visits followed, and culminated in India's purchasing more weapons from Israel, and the opening of a direct flight between India and Israel. Currently, India is Israel's third largest Asian trading partner since 2014 (Harel, 2015). The volume of trade exchange between them increased from \$200 million in 1992 to \$5 billion in 2021.

By following the volume of Israeli military exports to India, it is clear that India and Israel have bypassed the temporary ban imposed by the United States on military cooperation with India due to its military nuclear tests. India found the Israeli hand extended to it, especially in its ongoing conflict with Pakistan. Israel looks with an angry eye at the nuclear-armed Muslim-majority country with which Israel has no diplomatic relations. In 2015, Indian fighter jets bombed sites in Pakistan that were later discovered to have used Israeli missiles.

Currently, India is the largest buyer of Israeli military equipment. Israel has greatly contributed to the modernization of the Indian army's arsenal. Israeli military exports to India accounted for more than 7% of arms imports to India between 2012 and 2016. Israel's military support to India includes several technologies that India lacks. ((Staff, 2020).

A Comparison Of India's Interests Between Indo-Israeli Relations And Indo-Palestinian Relations:

In light of the gains that the Indian foreign policy seeks to achieve by seizing the changes that occur regionally in an attempt to obtain a better position for it among the great nations such as Russia, the United States and China. Therefore, India undertakes new moves on the basis that it guarantees the achievement of its economic, political and military goals.

When comparing the Israeli side with the Palestinian side, the following can be found:

First, the Interests of Relationship with the Israeli Side:

It is no secret to anyone that there are many gains that can be achieved by the Indian government.

1. Military and security interests:

It is known that the Israeli occupation state is advanced in these two fields, the military and the security fields. Israel has superior technology in this field that can help the Indian state in developing its security and military field.

Indo-Israeli military cooperation has become very evident. This is demonstrated by the volume of exchanges and deals in the military field between the two sides in the arms trade. The current balance will be in Israel's interest. At the same time, India is profiting from this by acquiring defense systems and weapons that other countries cannot supply (Sharma & Bing, 2015).

Combating terrorism: The Indian government is exploiting the ability of the Israeli entity to combat terrorism due to its expertise in this matter. Of course, Israel is taking advantage of India's constant need for this expertise, and the issue of Kashmir and the Indian government's attempt to control the situation in Kashmir makes it eager to obtain Israeli expertise.

In addition to Kashmir, the issue of the Indo-Pakistani conflict, where India is striving with all its might in order to fight the efforts in the State of Pakistan, which represents the natural enemy of India. One of the things that the Indian government mainly imports from Israel is the ability to use digital capabilities in the areas of attack and defense, and it is no secret that Israel is advanced in this field.

2. Space cooperation:

This is one of Israel's main areas of interest, in the field of space technologies, is the imaging capabilities that are being provided. It is related to the military and security field research used for military surveillance and border security. In recent decades India has developed home-made satellites with remote sensing features, meteorological data and communication capabilities and is launching them with its own missiles.

3. Finding interdependence in the economy:

Trade relations between India and Israel were maintained long before the establishment of formal diplomatic relations. A notable example is the diamond industry, which currently accounts for 50 percent of India's non-defense trade with Israel. Israel also specializes in the production of energy from non-conventional sources and the preservation of its resources. The Israelis are investing and setting up research and development facilities in India as well in the fields of medicine and biomedicine. Some of the biggest pharmaceutical companies like "Teva" or "Tero" have been operating in India for several years now. And prospects for cooperation and economic exchange are still open between the two countries (MEA, 2016).

Second, the interests of relationship with the Palestinian side:

The Indian leadership relies on using the relationship with the Palestinians as a gateway to a closer relationship with the Arab world. India has always had interests in the Arab countries, especially the Arab Gulf states, to import oil on the one hand and on the other hand, to provide a suitable environment for Indian labor abroad in the Arab Gulf states (Malik, 1991). The Palestinian issue is one of the concerns of Indian Muslims. From an actual point of view, specifically trade, the Indian-Palestinian relationship is weak when compared to India's trade relationship with Israel. The following is a summary of the reality of trade between India and Palestine issued in the year 2019.

Since, trade between India and Palestine is channelized through Israel, complete trade statistics are not available. Limited data suggests that India-Palestine annual bilateral trade is worth around US\$ 46.2 million (Indian exports: US \$ 46 million and Indian Imports: US \$ 153,000 according to figures given by Palestinian Ministry of National Economy). Indian exports include marble, granite and other stones, Basmati Rice, raw material for making vaccines, coffee, cashew nuts, sugar, sweet biscuits, sacks and bags for the packing of goods etc. Palestinian exports are mainly virgin olive oil and its fractions, dates etc. (Representative Office of India: Palestine, 2019, p. 4).

Conclusion:

Until the 1990s, Indian foreign policy was based on solidarity with the countries of the South under the flag of the Non-Aligned Movement. However, the policy of anonymity is not necessarily a foreign policy, but rather a tactical response to a particular disturbance in the power structures of the great powers. India's foreign policy design process is still a work in progress despite emerging trends and practices. The new directions of Indian diplomacy are visible to all. Domestic considerations of economic growth versus international relations are those that bring about changes in India's relations with Israel. On the other hand, relations with the Palestinians have become an integral part of India's extensive set of considerations. India has already shown a retreat from the voting pattern at the United Nations, which is a clear Palestinian arena of support. However, events such as the Israeli military operations in the Gaza Strip showed the complex situation that India faced. India is seeking to balance the new alliances it has formed with the countries involved in the conflict. India's shifting motives cannot be described as anti-Palestinian, because India is unlikely to relinquish Palestinian support that is in line with a number of core Indian values. Indian foreign policy under the Modi administration has complex consequences. Many of his rallies were praised, but nonetheless, his evasion of formulating a clear policy toward the Middle East was criticized.

It is clear that the course of Indo-Israel relations enjoys a special partnership that is multidimensional, multidisciplinary and comprehensive, characterized by trust and pragmatic diplomacy. All of this urges at the expense of Indo-Palestinian relations. However, gaps and differences in various issues still exist, and work is underway to overcome them. India and Israel have been able to create strong systems of international cooperation, are able to study and select joint initiatives in various fields in countries where the interests of the two countries can converge.

Both countries see that cooperation can be benefited from in many other areas. The prevailing view is that relations between India and Israel are based on a security, military and economic point of view, but the base is much broader and will continue to expand into other regions in the future. The full potential of India-Israel relations is yet to be realized and they can cooperate in many other areas in the coming years.

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